

Their melting points and other analytical data are mentioned in the paper on guanidines sent for publication in this journal.

3-Methyl-2-2'-benzothiazolylimino-4-thiazolidone. — N-Methyl-N'-2-benzothiazolylthiocarbamide (3.25 g.), monochloroacetic acid (1.5 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (3 g.) and absolute ethanol were refluxed together on a water bath for 8 to 10 hours and then poured into water, when a precipitate was formed. The precipitate was washed several times with hot water to remove unreacted monochloroacetic acid and sodium acetate. The product was crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 173°, yield 70%. (Found: N, 15.60; S, 24.60. $C_{11}H_9N_3OS_2$ requires N, 15.97; S, 24.33%).

The analytical data of other thiazolidones of this series are recorded in table I.

TABLE I

3-Alkyl-2-2'-(substituted benzothiazolyl) imino-4-thiazolidones

S.N.	Compounds benzothiazolylimino-4- thiazolidones	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen%		Sulphur%	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	3-Methyl-2-2'-(4 methyl)	198	$C_{12}H_{11}N_3OS_2$	15.00	15.16	23.41	23.11
2.	3-Methyl-2-2'-(6 methyl)-	193	$C_{12}H_{11}N_3OS_2$	14.90	15.16	22.90	23.11
3.	3-Ethyl-2-2'-	170	$C_{12}H_{11}N_3OS_2$	14.96	15.16	22.92	23.11
4.	3-Ethyl-2-2'-(4methyl)-	167	$C_{13}H_{13}N_3OS_2$	14.30	14.43	21.70	22.00
5.	3-Ethyl-2-2'-(6-methyl)-	178	$C_{13}H_{13}N_3OS_2$	14.21	14.43	21.60	22.00

2-Phenylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidone.—Phenylthiourea (7.6 g.) was heated under reflux with α -chloropropionic acid (5 ml.) in absolute ethanol in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate (8 g.) on a water bath for 4 to 5 hours. The excess of alcohol was distilled off and the product was poured into water which gave rise to the formation of a gummy substance, which solidified after a few hours on keeping in contact with water. The solid product was filtered, washed several times with water to remove sodium chloride produced in the reaction and the excess of sodium acetate. It was finally recrystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 139°, yield 70%. (Found: N, 13.70; S, 15.40. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2OS$ requires N, 13.59; S, 15.53%). Hydrochloride, m.p. 180°.

Similarly other 2-arylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidones were prepared from different asymmetric arylthioureas and α -chloropropionic acid and converted into their hydrochlorides as recorded in table II.

TABLE II

2-Arylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidones

S.N.	Aryl group R	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen%		Sulphur%		Hydro- chlorides M.P.(°C)
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
1.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	89	$C_{11}H_{12}N_2OS$	12.62	12.73	14.71	14.54	208
2.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	105.5	$C_{11}H_{12}N_2OS$	12.59	12.73	14.65	14.54	162
3.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	149	$C_{11}H_{12}N_2OS$	12.56	12.73	14.76	14.54	197
4.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	148	$C_{12}H_{14}N_2O_2S$	11.00	11.20	12.68	12.80	154

Fungicidal study of hydrochlorides of 2-arylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidones: The method employed consists of testing the ability of the fungicide at appropriate dilutions

to stop the germination and further growth of spores of a fungus, *Culvularia lunata*. The result is recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Fungicidal test of hydrochlorides of 2-arylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidones

Temp.—25°

No.	Aryl group	Concentrations		
		1:500	1:1000	1:10,000
		Percentage germination		
1.	Phenyl	nil	nil	45
2.	2- <i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	nil	nil	30
3.	2- <i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	nil	nil	30
4.	2- <i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	nil	nil	35
5.	2- <i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	nil	40	90

From the table, it is evident that the compounds were most active at the concentration of 1:500. The germination of spores was checked up to the concentration of 1:10,000. But beyond that, these compounds were almost inactive. The presence of CH₃-group in the nucleus enhances the fungicidal activity to a considerable extent while the presence of ethoxy group reduces its effectiveness.

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